

Climatic Change and Population Control

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ABSTRACT

The main reasons for climate change which are explained in this article are as follows: -Climate pollution by gases with CO₂ emission and Greenhouse Effect; Climate contamination of viruses with viruses from nature by animals or glaciers when thawing or produced in Laboratories; Induced Climate Change due to meteorological weapons with high intensity radio waves to produce rains, hurricanes and possible induction of earthquakes; Climate pollution by radiation due wars with irreversible consequences in the climate and Nuclear Winter; Climate Change due the explosion of missiles and atomic weapons in the oceans; Climate Change due the natural cyclical phases of the Earth affected by the cyclical variations of the Earth's magnetic field lines which can be affected by the severe cyclical activity of the sun due storms and sunspot because of the combustion that occurs inside the Sun which is due to the gravitational instabilities produced by the planets of the solar system, asteroids or the Comet Planet; Climate Change due to the invading Comet Planet into the solar system that affects with its gravitational field to the sun with solar storms and the planets with variation of the magnetic field lines affecting the climate, earthquakes and activation of volcanoes and indeed with the entry of many meteors and asteroids to the Earth; Climate change due to the Arm of God Allah explaining all the above reasons being more evident in times of Tribulation. The specific methods and devices of the control and manipulation of the population (inclusive to induce to the concupiscence) in times of new world order (Universal Big Brother Program for the control of human in the Earth) and possible Tribulation are explained in this article: Surveillance programs with all technological devices and networks used by humans systematic methods of persuasive manipulation and indoctrination used by some zombie humans and dark; Through the subjugation of employees and humans (inclusive children teaching them how to manipulate in the same style of the zombies); By enterprises or dark groups so that employees make manipulation games with details (investing work time to play like children) receiving bribes, money or labor benefits or with possible retaliation if they do not obey; Surveillance programs in living and working places with covert technological cameras, coincidence games, activities, plans and events programmed in sequence (inclusive pyrotechnic sounds in sequence); Covert numbers and words (in identification documents, cards, car plates, devices used by humans); Encrypted, hidden codes or small phrases and numbers not visible to the naked eye concealed in objects; Covert words in the speech of zombie humans and from multimedia and channels of traditional technological devices through movies, programs and even newscasts and inclusive to speak in code with the humans who know the surveillance programs and worst using in those channels and programs derogatory words against the Nazarenes (in the style of Nazism with the Jews) in complicity of close acquaintances, zombies and dark who participate profiting from the system for the vile metal; By means of an epidemic and viruses produced in laboratories creating epidemics and chaos in the Earth for the reduction and control of the population; Through strict restrictions and reduction of freedoms; Confinement with subsequent compulsory vaccination to be able to access human rights such as the right to work and the right to travel (with the cover-up of the respective organizations responsables for it: OIT OMT), without responsibility of the authorities in charge of vaccination worldwide (OMS) for the short or long term counterproductive effects of the vaccinated population due to the risk with the liquid of the vaccines by interfering with the DNA and RNA of the population; Possible marking and elimination of many humans (possibility of control of the pulmonary alveoly or induction controlled of diseases or pain due a virus by means of chips introduced in humans); Control of humans by the introduction of liquid and solid chips in humans (liquid crystals that crystallize in the organism and settle in neurons and receive ultrasonic waves of very low frequency) (possibly inserted from vaccines in global epidemiological programs for population control or invasive medical examination when this is not necessary as a figurative example of review of a patient with a sore in the mouth and introduction of the whole hand in the throat or prostate examination or specific injections to certain objective humans or Nazarenes who have opened the matrix of the darks and the elite that controls the humans in the Earth) in times of epidemic in medical examinations and treatments in hospitals (false medical negligence with breach of the medical oath of the use of Medicine for human good). The possible liquid and solid chips introduced into the human being can be used for mind reading (telepath) and thought induction (double direction: sending and receiving messages in the style of Stephen Hawking and the style of the technology already used in sending probes into space and to the moon) and possible human marking with surveillance program and the possible creation of zombie humans. Humans who have the mind reader chip installed can speak without speaking (the dumb speak playing like the miracles of Jesus Christ). It is possible to detect if the humans who have the mental reading chip installed have psychological alterations without going to a doctor. It is possible to know if humans are good or bad without seeing their actions and without going to a priest. In this way, human beings with the chip installed can be sanctioned before they do somewhat wrong (simply because it is known to be thinking). This can be used to know the fidelity to a political guideline or direction (this is known by the strong rumor in communist countries that already have the technology to detect the fidelity to the political party and possibly this is through this chip installed in the human being and mind reading). The inserted chip can also perform thought induction: this is possibly the apocalyptic mark mentioned in the apocalypse because many humans will perform sins or concupiscence induced and not naturally. Then, this will most probably activate the Wrath of God, the seals, and the trumpets of the apocalypse. It surprises me that actually the OMS wants to bring the vaccination program to Africa when in Africa there are not many dead by the epidemy (possibly for the control and reduction of the population will be in all the Earth). Afterward, the OMS mentioned that wants to insert a manufacturing center of vaccines in

many countries and inclusive vigilance programs (possibly for the control and reduction of the population will be effective at the local level). But, what the OMS needs to mention is that it is necessary to eliminate the laboratories of virus creation and not create more vaccine laboratories. Humans do not want more vaccine and injections and laboratories for the creation of vaccines but the elimination of virus laboratories which are most probably used for for the control and reduction of the population: thus, the reason for spreading a virus created in a laboratory across the Earth is evident: population reduction and control of humanity in preparation for a global elite program (new world order or program 2030 for the control of the dark and of the elite; Connection of covert surveillance cameras (in living and working places) with channels of traditional technological devices through movies, programs and even newscasts (including newscasts that usually make signs of dumb and deaf to those who have already discovered them) used by the dark with the respective programs and in addition, to monitor and tracing to verify the induction to concupiscence through mental reading (chips in humans) and surveillance cameras on line in the best style of James Bond espionage movies (including control of faces, pupils, irises, reflections, details and diseases); Games of judgments of sin against humans and Nazarenes (playing at being gods) and also profiting from the vile metal through the system and contributing to the persecution of the Nazarenes; Fake judgments of sin against humans and Nazarenes because many of these sins have been induced with technology due the possible induction of thoughts by the liquid cristal settle in neurons and have not been natural (dark inducing sin through technology and playing gods to induce evil and destruction of intimacy and privacy even in the mind of the human being); Retaliation to those who report the surveillance and manipulation programs and marking of humans for mind reading (telepathy) and thought induction (making them sick sending to the hospitals or removing them); Digital identification plan and digital money to do digital control and avoid conflict and protests of marked and Nazarenes in surveillance programs who discover that there is no privacy in their documents and inclusive in their mind (telepathy: mind reading and thought induction: artificial intelligence): it surprises that EU mention that has a digital plan for europeans for digital control on line. But, before the epidemic, Europe and the world advanced a lot in technology and the data of humans are digitally in hospitals and institutes that humans need. After, the EU mentions artificial intelligence for human beings. Then and in vaccination and epidemic time, it is possible that the digital control is a new digital control with artificial intelligence and with possible chips installed in the human being (possibly already installed in many human beings); Games of events and coincidences to cause accidents or conflicts in the life of marked, target or Nazarenes (change games of victim to accused by companies that regulate the order with subsequent rectification of the game made by the same companies when the Nazarenes claim); Games of recognition of the identity of human beings (in the style of the movie Unknown) by enterprises and service stations which are necessary for the daily movement of human beings creating conflicts of manipulation and stress in the marked or Nazarenes Salary payment games (payment of wages with dinners and game of check payment) creating manipulation conflicts and stress in the life of marked, target or Nazarenes Programmed plans of theft and scams of enterprises and humans even knowing of the surveillance cameras for the control of the marked, target or Nazarenes. Then, there is severe control of human beings in their daily activities to verify the follow-up of the matrix and darks that plan situations of concupiscence in the human being. Besides, this is occurring in coincidence with an accelerated new world order program and possible tribulation times and possibly already with the installation of the apocalyptic mark (possible chips introduced in the human being for mind reading and thought induction to induce concupiscence) in humans mentioned in the apocalypse for dark control of humans.

The global forms of the severe manipulation and population control in times of new world order and Tribulation are explained in this article are as follows: By increasing taxes; Through armed conflicts and wars create discord, wars and chaos between countries (often bordering countries with the same origins and with the same culture: Russia and Ukraine: war motivated by US OTAN EU); To later usurp its resources (oil energy resource: US Iraq Kuwait); To later control them politically and economically (US Iraq Kuwait) and when these power or developed countries cannot control or usurp their resources, they begin to block them economically (Russia in the war between Russia and Ukraine where besides developed countries influence in the war by printing additional money to use for the war causing imbalance and global economic crisis instead of looking for ways to avoid it) in order to cause chaos and economic crisis with the knowledge and complicity of the world organizations responsible (OEA ONU) and make the population believe that the cause of the economic crisis is the government in power. However, some countries have resisted these blockades (Cuba Venezuela Nicaragua Russia China) and managed to show that it is possible to have governments independent of the control of these powers or countries that believe they own the Earth; To put rulers (governing) of interest in the same countries in conflict; To control them using the pretext of placing military bases in the countries in conflict (NATO OTAN: military bases in some European countries, US military bases: in some South American countries and some countries of Europe). In addition, this is preferable to reduce military bases in other countries and reduction of nuclear weapons, and use the financial resources for the reduction of inequity and poverty on the Earth. Thus, the organizations responsible for the proliferation of nuclear weapons (OIEA) have played an ineffective and passive (cover-up) role, which has caused the risk of a third nuclear world war to be imminent); Through the war against terror: however and actually, this is a false speech used to point to countries that oppose the control or directive of the powers and that have a culture or political structure different from that of the powers and later make conflict and war to later control them or usurp their resources (some Arab and Muslim countries, for example, US, Irak, Lybia and blaming an entire country for terrorism and occupying for years (Afganistán)).

In this way and actually, some countries have developed nuclear weapons (North Korea, Iran) to protect themselves in some way and thus, the same thing does not happen to them as to the countries mentioned above (Irak, Lybia) and that have been destroyed with the false discourse of the war against terror. In this way, the best thing is to have good relations with all the countries of the Earth which are again summed in the Bible [1] in a message: Love your brother (all human beings) as yourself! (Mt.22-39) (and not to go around the Earth pointing out terrorists to any country that opposes its guidelines). Therefore, it is possible to reduce the economic resources for the war against terror which can be used to reduce poverty and inequity in human beings; Through the war against drugs: there are many other substances and products consumed by humans that can be harmful to health and that are allowed and have not become a vice (when something is forbidden: this increases the interest in obtaining it explained from the beginning of creation in Genesis [1]: an apple from the tree of good and evil in the garden of Eden: Adam and Eve).

In addition, many countries have allowed the use of certain types of drugs for medical purposes (Uruguay, Bolivia) where drug use has gone unnoticed in these countries; Through religion: with a structure of religion that tries to control the population through a guideline and speeches that obey the Vatican and the actual governments of each country (which is evident when there are countries such as Nicaragua that do not follow a guideline of the church and the elite and then, the religion surprisingly actively intervenes in politics): the conclusion is reached and to which many humans have reached, that religion is a power most actually used (along with political and economic power); Through political power by means of the false argument used by politicians to reduce inequity and poverty: where a large amount of resources and money have been allocated to the political powers and rulers of many countries for centuries by the respective organizations responsible (FMI BM) without any results and in many countries poverty and inequity have increased. Besides, the bureaucracy is a structure of order and rules of management and administration used within the governments of each country that contribute to the inefficiency and manipulation of the required procedures in human life that ultimately affect the life of each human being when they require formalities that end up being complicated and time-consuming. Then, this power structure in politics, economics, and religion for the control of the population is ineffective and obeys the interests of the dark who control humans

on the Earth, and is used ineffectively by the rulers (governing) of the countries who come to power precisely with the false discourse of reducing poverty and inequity; Through the pretext of climate change: severe climate change due to the emission of CO₂ and the greenhouse effect is a complete fallacy. The world organizations involved with the climate (ONU) try to make humanity believe that this is the reason for the severe climatic changes that the human being has experienced on the Earth to obtain economic resources and avoid mentioning God in control of the Earth and course the climate and to avoid mentioning the Omnipotence of God [1] in the control of the Earth and the climate: the severe climate change is frequently due to solar storms and variations in the magnetic field lines of the Earth because of gravitational variations in the solar system or due to the entry of an asteroid or Comet Planet what is controlled and all the Universe by God. Therefore, the climate change is controlled by the Eternal God (which is explained in the Bibles with a lot of examples with Moses, Josue, Hezekiah) and thus, this is better to use the resources and money for so-called climate change to reduce poverty and inequity in the Earth and increase equity in humans: Human Beings must not believe everything said by the organizations and individuals that control the humans in the Earth and that obey the directions imposed within the matrix triangle of control of the Earth; Through the sport by means of the persuasive manipulation of observers or attendees at sporting events through commercials programs, commentators (hidden words and numbers in speech), players participating in the match: with gestures or sequence of plays, numbers, words or details in the players uniform, referees (make decision of plays in favor of a team purposely: false bad arbitration) or leading organizers committing sports corruption not applying the rules or discriminating players (Serbian, Russian and Belarusian tennis players at tennis competitions due to some tennis organizations) or teams (Russian sports clubs and inclusive the Russian national team due FIFA decision) at convenience. Besides, when there are countries in conflict or war: instead of uniting the countries in conflict by means of the sport, the respective organizations (FIFA UEFA) discriminate and increase the conflict: discriminating and not allowing the participation of tennis players (including top tennis players), Football Countries and Sport Clubs in international competitions for reasons of restrictions due to the epidemic, conflict or war (including countries that organized previous World Cups: Russia) where the interest, quality and love for this sport has increased and that must be used to unite human beings and countries and not to not allow them to participate: which increases the division and conflict between countries or humans: This is important to highlight and value the position of the ATP for deciding that the ATP does not agree that athletes from certain countries (Russia and Belarus) cannot participate in international tournaments stating that this is against the principles of merit and non-discrimination: then, this is tremendously criticizable that the organization responsible of Football (FIFA UEFA) participates in armed conflicts or war with discriminatory decisions in Football, increasing the war by not allowing countries in conflict to participate in World Cup of Football: FIFA slogan of no to racism and some form of discrimination is a complete farce and used for convenience and interest (in the same style of all the other organizations (mainly ONU, OEA, FMI, BM, VATICAN) that control humans and that in 2000 years of the coming of the Envoy of God have not been able to solve iniquity and poverty), discrimination that has been evident in the conflict between Russia and Ukraine: Football is the main sport in the Earth and it is the one that can unite human beings the most and should be used as a source of union and not division; Through education: where this is used by many countries to induce and manipulate their inhabitants in a certain political direction through the dissemination of knowledge and even the textbooks of the students: many underdeveloped countries have increased illiteracy and degradation in education because this favors the politicians of the country's government: having an ignorant people who do not see what they do with the country's money and who cannot criticize them: the greatness of peoples depends on the education that gives the independence of individuals who are the ones that make the country advance; Through world organizations to control countries: ONU, OEA, Vatican, OTAN, UE: many countries have to obey the guidelines of these organizations, which often do not respond to the needs of the citizens of each country: many institutions in the countries must obey the organizations (the Vatican for the religion) in a rigid way, which is often not in accordance with the situation of the country's citizens, who often need new variants or guidelines (some organizations can cause chaos, conflict or war as for example the war of Russia with Ucraina where the possible annexation of Ucraina to the OTAN and UE is one of the reasons for the war between these two countries. Therefore, there would be no war between these two countries where without those organizations); Through world organizations of espionage (CIA, FBI, KGB, Gestapo, SS): employing persuasive interference in the countries and rulers of some undeveloped countries (some South America and Center America countries and some European, Asia and Africa countries) with the objective of the power countries of control, manipulate or destabilize countries and inclusive simple humans (using the personal data of thousands of people around the world). Through the control and intervention of the Creator God Allah which is necessary and essential in times of Tribulation at the time timely (Holy Bible: Apoc. 6 Apoc. 8:6 Apoc. 5 Apoc. 7 Apoc. 21) due to everything mentioned in this scientific research respect to the control and manipulation of the population (regarding the increase of inequity, discord, and evil among humans) which is not following the guideline given by the envoy of God 2000 years ago: Jesus Christ. **Keywords:** God, Allah, Jesuchrist, Bible, Creator, Education, Climate change, Population Control, Climate Pollution, Gases CO₂, Greenhouse Effect, Epidemic, Viruses, Laboratory, Zombies, Dark, Elite, new world order, OMS, ONU, OEA, Vatican, OTAN, UE, FMI, BM, OIT, OMT, Meteorological weapons, Haarp, Sura, Wars, Sport, Religion, Radiation, Nuclear Winter, Sun, Magnetic field lines, Storms, Asteroids, Comet Planet, Volcanoes, Climate Catastrophies, Tribulation, Taxes, Terror, Drugs, Organizations, Inequity, Poverty, Manipulation, Indoctination, Technological Devices, Covert technological devices, networks, Newscasts, Surveillance programs, Big Brother Program, Digital Identification Plan, Digital Money, Covert numbers and covert words, Encrypted, Hidden codes or small phrases not visible to the naked eye, Covert words in the speech of zombie humans in multimedia and traditional technological devices, Nazism, Jews, Coincidence games, Activities, Plans, Events Programmed in sequence, Pyrotechnic sounds in sequence, Games of events and coincidences to cause accidents or conflicts, Games of judgments of sin against humans and Nazarenes, Games of recognition of the identity of human beings, Unknown, Companies, Service stations, Salary payment games, Programmed plans of theft and scams of companies and enterprises, Retaliation, Marking, Reduction, False medical negligence, Medical oath, Medicine, Liquid and solid chips in humans, Liquid crystals, Neurons, Ultrasonic waves, Vaccines, Global epidemiological programs, Matrix, Dark, Elite, Mind Reading, Telepath, Thought induction, Apocalypse, Wrath of God.

Climate Change

The most representative human catastrophes that have occurred on the Earth are: the crucifixion of the Envoy of God, Noah's flood, the destruction of Sodom and Gomorrah by an asteroid or by asteroids and meteorites pushed by the passage of the Comet Planet, the extinction of dinosaurs and some species of animals by asteroid or by asteroids and meteorites pushed by the passage of the Comet Planet, accident of the Chernobyl nuclear reactor in the USSR, the explosion of nuclear weapons in Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan, World War I and II and

extermination of a large part of the Jews by the Nazis, the black plague of Europe, impact of the twin towers of New York by planes, COVID Epidemic by a virus created in the laboratory for reduction and control of humanity, chaotic climate in times of the beginning of the new world order and Tribulation.

Concerning climatic change, there are six different opinions about the reasons for the actual climate change:

1.- Climate pollution by gases with CO₂ emission and the increase of the Greenhouse Effect: whose causes are: consumption of non-renewable energy, destruction of ecosystems, transportation and fossil combustion with CO₂ emissions due to the use of oil, coal and natural gas by industries and factories.

Nevertheless, the Greenhouse effect is a natural phenomenon and beneficial to us: certain gases present in the atmosphere retain part of the thermal radiation emitted by the earth's surface after being heated by the sun, maintaining the temperature of the Earth at a level suitable for the development of life [7].

But, the increment of Greenhouse gases increases the retention of heat. Therefore, if the concentration of gases increases, then the natural Greenhouse effect increases with the increase of the temperature and global warming of the Earth which leads to a climate change with consequences as for example: global warming and increase of temperature, increase of floods, rise in the sea level, increase of devastating hurricanes and tornadoes, forest fires, desertification of fertile áreas and droughts with impact on agriculture and livestock, forced migration of certain species of animals and birds.

Nevertheless, there are other reasons which are explained in detail in the following ítems that contribute with more percentage to the chaotic climate because there are places on the Earth with droughts and increases in the temperatures where there is not much climate pollution by gases.

In addition, it is actually happening that there are simultaneously some places on the Earth with temperature increases and some places with temperature decreases, which cannot be explained by CO₂ pollution on the Earth.

Therefore, the chaotic climate due to the CO₂ emission and Greenhouse effect is a complete fallacy. Evidently, the world organizations (ONU) involved with the climate try to make humanity believe that it is the reason for the chaotic climate that human beings have experienced on Earth.

This should not be surprising, because these organizations receive economic funding to show humanity that it is the reason for climate change.

Therefore, human beings must not believe everything said by organizations and individuals who are ruling the humans on Earth and who obey directions imposed by the dark within the matrix triangle of control of the Earth.

Nevertheless, the warming of the atmosphere by CO₂ due to the consumption by industries and factories is increasing but still, it is a small percentage of the chaotic climate.

However, it is very important to diminish this percent as much as we can but because of reasons of consideration and respect for nature and the Creation of God.

2.- Induced Climate Change due to meteorological weapons (high-intensity radio waves) with the aim of changing the climate (rains, hurricanes, tornadoes) and with possible induction of earthquakes: Haarp Antennas (American Technology) & Sura Antennas (Russian Technology)

Other factor is the intervention of the humans or the elite who control the Earth in the human life in different forms which is evident for all humans living during the epidemy: Control of Population with systematic methods of persuasive indoctrination and manipulation networks with technological devices, covert surveillance cameras and zombies human who obey the dark and manipulate with details to the Nazarenes & during the epidemic through strict restrictions and methods of reducing freedoms: confinement with subsequent compulsory vaccination to be able to access human rights such as the right to work and the right to travel example (with the cover-up of the respective organizations responsables for it: OIT OMT), without responsibility of the authorities in charge of vaccination worldwide (OMS) for the short or long term counterproductive effects of the vaccinated population due to the risk with the liquid of the vaccines by interfering with the DNA and RNA of the population: possible mind reading (telepathy) and induction of thoughts (by means of liquid crystals that crystallize in the organism and installed in neurons and that send or receive very low frequency ultrasonic waves): possible human marking with program of surveillance to marked and possible creation of zombie humans for population control for the dark in the new world order and in times of Tribulation.

Therefore, there is also the possibility of the intervention of humans in the climate by using the technology for different motives positive or negative and thus, the climatic change is a climate scam as for example: the Gloria Storm that has hit Catalonia was it a punishment by the nature itself? or it was a nature coincidence? (apparent coincidence because everything and nature indeed is controlled by the Eternal) or by some technology that can affect the climate?

For example, it is possible to change the climate with some positive purpose with the actual technology. Actually, this is known in some countries that bombard the clouds to generate rain to improve agriculture.

Therefore, it is possible to affect the climate to generate rain or change climate conditions for a positive reason.

Actually, there is also a country that tries to create an artificial sun by nuclear fusion reactor but with no successful result regarding its application and with enough risk for nature and humans.

Then, it is not possible to try to imitate the Eternal in the Creation of the main star: the Sun that illuminates humans daily and indeed: illumination with mercy because it illuminates good and bad humans [1].

Besides, the technology can also be used to generate chaotic climates and even earthquakes. The important question is: is it possible to change or to do some chaotic effect on the climate with the actual technology?

Actually, there is a strong rumor of the existence of Haarp Technology (American Technology) or Sura Technology (Russian Technology) which emits high-intensity radio waves to produce chaotic climate and inclusive earthquakes. There is also the rumor of earthquakes caused in some countries destabilize them or for other dark reasons (one of these strong rumors is the Haiti earthquake).

Then, this technology is possible to use as a meteorological weapon which is terrible for the humans who live on the Earth: simple humans within a country affected by an earthquake or chaotic climate thinking of natural causes without knowing that this is due to the climate technology!!

3.- Climate change due to nuclear wars: Nuclear Winter: Chaos & Climate Catastrophe in the Earth with irreversible consequences, Climate Change due to missiles and atomic weapons detonated in the different oceans affecting the stability of the oceans and producing the activation of submarine volcanoes (Nature by means of God Allah rebels in the short or long term.!!)

The historical development of ionizing radiation is shown in the next table [4], [5]:

1895	The x-rays are discovered by Röntgen and the first x-ray image is produced
1896	The radioactivity in uranium is discovered by Becquerel
1898	Marie and Pierre Curie identify radioactive elements: radio, thorium and polonium
1901	First medical uses of radioactive substances. Danlos and Block located radius in tuberculous skin lesions
1918	Rutherford observed constituents of the atomic nucleus
1923	George de Hevesey performed studies of the first biological tracers with radioactive material in plants and rats
1928	Formation of the International Commission of Radiological Protection (ICRP)
1930	Lawrence and Livingstone built the first cyclotron for accelerated charged atomic particles
1934	Fermi produced artificial radioactivity
1942	First controlled nuclear fission reaction, Chicago
1945	First atomic bomb detonated in the Los Alamos desert, New Mexico
1945	First atomic bomb launched in Hiroshima and Nagasaki
1948	Emilio Segré discovers and gives its name to the first radioactive element artificial Technetium 99m, California, US
1954	Thermonuclear bomb detonated, Bikini Island, Pacific Ocean
1954	Industrial scale development of a nuclear power reactor, Obninsk, Russia
1957	Accidental radiation release, Windscale, UK
1964	Anger invented the gamma camera for radionuclide imaging
1972	Godfrey Hounsfield patented computed tomography X-rays (CT), UK
1979	Three Mile Island reactor accident, US
1986	Reactor incident in Chernobyl, USSR

A table of radiation types with their respective effects is shown in the next table:

Radiation	Type	Units	Effects
Nuclear Radiation, Gamma rays, X-rays, High energy	Ionizing	Joule, KeV, MeV	Ionization, rupture of chemical and molecular bonds, DNA damage, genotoxic

Ultraviolet			effects
Low energy Ultraviolet, Visible light, Infrared	Non-Ionizing	nm, μ m, cm	Electronic excitation, rotation and vibration of molecules, biochemical and heating effects
Microwave, Radiofrequency	Non-Ionizing	Hertz, Hz	Severe induced currents, vibration and rotation of molecules, heating
Magnetic and Electric Field, High Voltage Network	Non-Ionizing	Hertz, Hz	Small induced currents, various cellular effects, neurological and behavioral reactions

The electromagnetic spectrum with different radiation-generating devices is shown below:

1 Hz- 300 kHz: LF, ELF (low and very low-frequency radiation): Device electric fields, electrical network, AM frequency radio sections, video monitors ($3-3 \times 10^4$ Hz).

300 KHz-300 MHz: RF (radiofrequency): AM radio sections, FM radio, Medical shortwave (27 MHz), NMR: magnetic resonance (2.13 MHz for the magnetic field of 1 T (Tesla)).

300 MHz-300 GHz: M.O. (microwave): Household appliances use of microwave, mobile telephony (900 MHz, 1800 MHz), radar, microwave for medical physiotherapy: 2450 MHz and 915 MHz.

300 GHz (1 mm) -780 nm: IR (infrared): Sunlight, laser, heat therapy equipment.

780 nm-400 nm (Visible light): Sunlight, laser, phototherapy.

400 nm-100 nm: UV (ultraviolet): Sunlight, materials above 2700 K, radiotherapy treatments, food and air sterilization, fluorescent tubes.

1 eV-200 keV: X-rays: X-rays tubes, synchrotron, accelerator.

200 keV (or less) -.....: X-rays devices, Gamma rays devices, Radioactive isotopes, Nuclear radiation, nuclear reactors, cosmic rays, (explosions of supernovae or nuclei of active galaxies which do not reach the earth's surface as the high atmosphere absorbs them).

It is customary to express the non-ionizing radiation of lower energy by its frequency (Hz) (radio frequencies and microwaves), the infrared (IR) regions, visible light and ultraviolet (UV) by its wavelength (nm), and the ionizing electromagnetic radiation (Rem) (X-rays and gamma rays) for its energy (keV or MeV) [4], [5].

The radiation consists of the energy transfer from a source to the environment without the necessary presence of a medium. The interaction between radiation with matter produces some biological and non-biological effects in humans such as lesions, erythema and burns, cancers, genetic malformations and catastrophic effects on the climate. These effects are based on the kind of wave, the particle energy, the particle type (ionizing or nonionizing) and the material or medium with which the radiation impacts [4], [5].

The ionizing radiation causes the separation of electrons from atoms and molecules and ionizes them. This ionization can change the chemical and biological conditions in a molecule.

Nonionizing radiation does not have sufficient energy to convert molecules or atoms to ions, but it can produce heat (seemingly reversible) to the molecules. The heating is due to the rotation, vibration and movement of the molecules. This heating is used for therapeutic and aesthetic effects. The biological effects of this radiation are actually under investigation. However, it can cause injuries, burns and erythema.

☼ **Effects of the ionizing radiation in the climate due to Nuclear war: Nuclear Winter**

In a nuclear war, the nuclear detonations on the surface would propel fine particles high up into the stratosphere. Most of the dust and particles would be carried by the fireball itself. A fraction would be sucked up by the stem of the mushroom cloud. Even the most modest explosions in or above cities would produce massive fires as occurred in Hiroshima and Nagasaki.

The resulting smoke is far more dangerous for the climate than the dust. Those fires would consume wood, oil, plastic, roof tar, natural gas and a wide variety of other fuels. Two kinds of smoke would be generated. Simmering is a flameless, low-temperature fire that produces finely oily, bluish-white organic particles such as cigarette smoke. In contrast, in flaming combustion, when there is an adequate supply of oxygen, the burning organic material converts a significant part to elemental carbon, and the sooty smoke is very dark. Soot is one of the blackest materials in nature that can be produced. Like in an oil refinery fire or a pile of burning car tires or any big city fire, great clouds of murky, ugly, dark, sooty smoke would rise high above the cities, in the case of nuclear war [7].

High-altitude dust particles would reflect additional sunlight back into space and cool Earth somewhat. More important are the dense black curtains in the upper part of the atmosphere, blocking sunlight from reaching the lower atmosphere, where mainly Greenhouse gases reside. These gases are therefore deprived of their influence on the global climate. The Greenhouse effect decreases and the Earth's surface becomes much cooler [7].

Since cities and oil deposits are so rich in combustible materials, it doesn't take many nuclear explosions on them to get a huge amount of smoke to darken the entire Northern Hemisphere and beyond. If the dark clouds of soot are almost opaque and cover a large area, then the Greenhouse Effect may almost completely disappear. In the most likely scenario that some sunlight got through, the temperature would still drop by 10 to 20 degrees Celsius or more, depending on the season and local geography. In many places, it could be as dark at noon as it is on a moonless night before the nuclear war started. The resulting environmental changes can last for years [7].

If the Greenhouse Effect is a blanket that we wrap around ourselves to keep warm, what nuclear winter actually does is remove that blanket back. The aforementioned darkening and cooling of the Earth that would follow a nuclear war along with secondary climatic and radioactive consequences is what we call nuclear Winter [7].

A typical temperature for a point on the Earth's land surface, averaged without regard to latitude, season, and time of day, is approximately 15 degrees Celsius. In the case of no Greenhouse Effect, the resulting temperature would be about -20 degrees Celsius. The difference between the planetary environment with and without the Greenhouse

Effect is equivalent to the difference between clement conditions and a deep freeze. Then, playing with the Greenhouse Effect, especially things that reduce it like dark clouds of soot and dust particles due to nuclear winter in a nuclear war, can be very risky [7].

If the actual concentration of carbon dioxide CO₂ from the Earth's Greenhouse in the Earth's atmosphere were doubled, as it will be in a few decades if the actual trends continue, the Earth's surface temperature is likely to increase by a few degrees due to the solar radiation retained by carbon dioxide CO₂ from the Earth's Greenhouse. After a major volcanic eruption, the temperature can drop by at most a few degrees due to ash, sulfur gases, and fine clouds of sulfuric acid droplets that reduce the Greenhouse Effect. During the ice age, the global temperature was a few degrees cooler, approaching the freezing point of water.

In a nuclear winter, depending on its severity, temperatures could get even colder, reaching well below freezing. The effects of low temperatures, fires, radioactive fallout and climate chaos that occur in a nuclear winter represent the most serious climatic catastrophe that can occur during the existence of humans on the Earth [7].

☐ Phases of Nuclear Winter

The phases of nuclear winter due to the radiation and side effects of a nuclear explosion are [7]:

- 1.- A nuclear explosion of a few megatons explodes a few kilometers above a city. The fireball's radiation, traveling at the speed of light, ignites flammable structures in a circle a few miles from the city center. The shock wave traveling at the speed of sound has not yet reached the city.
- 2.- As the shock wave leaves the city, most of the skyscrapers and buildings have collapsed. The fires have been extinguished momentarily because of the shock wave and the smoke is sucked out of the city. Above the stage, the mushroom cloud is visible, sucking debris at high altitudes into the lower stratosphere.
- 3.- The shock wave has passed. Many fires started by the fireball and others ignited by broken or demolished gas lines are raging.
- 4.- The fires spread over hundreds of square kilometers and above the fires, large clouds of black smoke rise.
- 5.- Hell has become a firestorm. A large column of convective air establishes itself, sucking the flames upward and carrying the smoke to high altitudes. Firestorm winds can exceed hurricane force.
- 6.- Many days later, a large column of smoke and soot is observed over the city, which extends through the stratosphere. Thus, the simultaneous development and subsequent spreading and merging of many such smoke and soot clouds at various heights can lead to a nuclear winter.

In resume, the consequences of Nuclear Winter due to nuclear explosion are: decrease in temperature, cold, cooling and continental frosts, darkening of the sky, invisibility of the sun, moon and stars, reduction of incoming solar radiation to the Earth, decrease in sunlight and solar brightness with decrease in photosynthesis affecting plants and trees with ecological impact, decrease in the ozone layer with partial recovery of solar brightness due to the increase in ultraviolet light that the sun emits affecting the skin of humans, impact on agriculture with reduced harvests and livestock, radioactive fallout, fires and explosions of refineries and oil facilities, toxicity, pyrotoxins,

smoke emissions, soot rain, the outbreak of pandemics and famine, economic crisis and recession, droughts, reduction of humans and extinction of some species of animals and plants, destruction of the ecosystem [7].

In conclusion, the effects of the Nuclear Winter on humans, the ecosystem and the climate are catastrophic and probably irreversible.

In this way, it can be said to confirm what was mentioned by Einstein himself: If the third world war between humans is nuclear and with nuclear missiles, the fourth world war between humans will be with stones and sticks. Practically, a nuclear world war is an apocalypse on Earth.

Effect of radiation on humans

The radiation produced from a nuclear war is ionizing radiation. In humans, the ionizing radiation randomly collides with atoms and molecules expelling electrons of them as it passes through living cells giving rise to ions and free radicals that break chemical bonds, and cause other molecular changes that damage affected cells in the interaction. In the case of tissues, the biological effects of ionizing radiation mainly result from damage caused to the nucleus of cells, mainly to DNA causing a mutation in its genetic code and cancer. Severe DNA damage can kill cells, resulting in tissue damage or death. Minor DNA damage can result in permanent changes in cells, which can cause cancer. In addition, damage to other tissues and organs can occur, as well as burns, erythema and lesions. The embryo and the child are the most vulnerable. If those changes occur in reproductive cells, this can lead to inherent changes, a phenomenon called mutation [4], [5].

Therefore, all known risks of exposure to the ionizing portion of the electromagnetic spectrum are the results of the breaking of chemical bonds in the DNA. The clinical manifestations of the lesions are on: the skin, the bone marrow and the lymphoid tissue, the intestine, the gonads, the respiratory system, the lens of the eye, and other tissues.

The skin is the first barrier that radiation finds in the body, although there may also be cases of inhalation or ingestion of radioactive substances. The cells of the basal layer of the skin are the most radiosensitive and they are reached by very low energy radiations, even from the range of ultraviolet radiation which also occurs in a nuclear winter due to the depletion of the ozone layer. Consequently, skin lesions are the most frequent of all radio-induced histopathological reactions [4], [5].

In summary, exposure to ionizing radiation can lead to injuries with fatal results in inherited disorders, birth defects and cancers which appear within decades, years or months. The extent of the injury and the effects such as skin burns depends on the type of radiation as well as the exposure conditions and doses. These effects are found in radiotherapy patients or people with severe irradiation or nuclear accidents or atomic bombs [4], [5].

After the nuclear tests in Nevada (1950), children from southwest Utah and Nevada who were exposed to radioactive rain showed an increase in the frequency of thyroid cancer. In addition, a test of thermonuclear weapons in Bikini Atoll, in 1954, produced also a frequency increase in thyroid cancer among the inhabitants of the Marshall Islands. The increase was proportional to the received dose in the thyroid gland in childhood due to the high levels of radioactive fallout [4], [5].

Besides, Bequerel, cesium, strontium and iodine were released into the environment in the Windscale reactor accident in the United States in 1957. The reactor was a product of plutonium with uranium fuel. The maximum absorbed dose outside the installation was about 35 μGy /h. It was forbidden to consume milk in areas near the installation. In addition, fourteen workers received doses between 30 mSv and 46 mSv per quarter during reactor control.

The Nuclear accident in 1958 at the Laboratory of Los Alamos, New Mexico, United States caused a fatal radiological injury to an employee. The average body exposure was around 49 Gy. The symptoms included: physical collapse, semi-consciousness, abdominal pain, anoxia, hypotension, circulatory failure, irritability and antagonism. Clinical-pathological alterations were observed in the urinary and hematopoietic systems. Leukocyte count changes were the indicator of severe irradiation.

In addition, three people were seriously exposed in the accident of the Van de Graff Accelerator in the Gulf Oil accelerator accident in the United States in 1967: the first received about 1 Gy in the whole body, the second about 3 Gy in the whole body, and the third approximately 6 Gy in the whole body, 30 Gy in the feet and 60 Gy in the hands. The symptoms were: nausea, vomiting and muscle aches.

The accident of the SL-1 reactor prototype, in Idaho, United States in 1961 was used for the production of electrical energy. Three victims were registered, as a result of the high activity fission.

On other hand, the physical and sanitary personnel had enough experience in the accident of Three Mile Island, United States, in 1979, but the consequences resulting from the accident were so many that it was not possible to solve all issues. This accident caused the release of 7.4 TBq of Iodine 131 and levels of strontium 90 and Cesium 137.

The Radiological accident of Goiania in Brazil occurred in 1985. The ^{137}Cs teletherapy unit was stolen in a clinic in Goiania. The fountain capsule was broken during disassembly and in one part of the city, Cesium 137 chloride powder was diffused. The parts of the fountain assembly and the dust of Cs 137 which glowed in the dark with bluish color were sold to several families, who developed gastrointestinal symptoms. In addition, the patients developed skin lesions. Approximately 249 people suffered contamination with many requiring hospitalization. The absorbed dose was between 4 and 7 Gy.

Furthermore, 1900 PBq of fission and fuel products were released for 10 days in the accident at the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant in Ukraine (1986). The radioactive isotopes released were Iodine 131, Strontium 90, and Cesium 137. The main risks consisted of ingestion of contaminated food and external irradiation due to surface deposition. This accident doubled the total number of deaths worldwide caused by radiological accidents (61). In the Chernobyl accident, radioactive material was released, and radiological diseases and burns occurred in more than 200 people. The long-term effects are not predictable, but estimates assume that around 30,000 additional deaths from cancer can occur during the next 70 years due to the accident. In addition, children of Belarus and Ukraine who were contaminated by radionuclides released in the Chernobyl accident showed an increased incidence of thyroid cancer.

In resume, there were over 285 accidents in nuclear reactors in different countries with 1350 affected and 33 fatalities from 1945 to 1987. More accidents have occurred in installations with sources for radiotherapy. Important information has also been obtained from nuclear plant accidents such as the Chernobyl (1986) and the Three Mile Island nuclear reactor (1979).

The production of the atomic bomb has had dramatic consequences in the history of humanity. Important scientific information has been obtained from the events that occurred in Japan in August 1945, from the Japanese survivors of the explosion of nuclear weapons in Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan during World War II. Many of the deaths were due to explosions and burns but, in the following approximate thirty years, 500 cases of radiation-induced cancer and leukemia were reported [4], [5].

Therefore, it is important to know the Dose limit for the whole body, hands, skin and eyes are [4], [5]:

	Dose limit (European Commission)	
	Workers (Radiation)	Members of the public
Whole Body	20 mSv/year	1 mSv/year
Hands, Skin	500 mSv/year	50 mSv/year
Eyes	150 mSv/year	15 mSv/year

Besides, it is important to follow all safety and radiation protections against ionizing radiation. Shields are used to limit the dose which enters the tissue and thus the attenuation is the maximum possible. The shields to use depending on the type of particle are aluminum, concrete, tantalum, platinum, lead steel.

The next table shows the shields to use depending on the type of particle [4], [5]:

	Shields
Electrons	Low Z (atomic number) materials: aluminum or concrete
Ions	High Z (atomic number) materials: tantalum or platinum
X-rays and gamma rays	Ordinary concrete, roller door steel, shield lead
Neutrons	Ordinary concrete

Climate Change due to the detonation of atomic weapons and missiles in the different oceans affects the stability of the oceans and the activation of submarine volcanoes (Nature (God Allah!!) rebels in the short or long term!!).-

Detonation of atomic weapons and missiles in the different oceans of the Earth is also a reason for the climatic change. Actually, a large number of missiles and atomic weapons have been detonated in the different oceans of

the Earth due to the actual risk of war between different countries. Then, it has affected the stability of the oceans and the activation of submarine volcanoes, which are also reasons for climate change and seismic activations: Nature (God Allah!!) rebels in the short or long term...!! [1].

4.- Climate contamination of viruses by sea and air

Human beings have had some epidemics due to viruses with catastrophic consequences for example the Spanish Flu originated from animals possibly rodents or the marmot through fleas that carry the bacteria of this disease from an infected rodent.

On other hand, humans were also infected by the Black Death through fleas of rodents and with respiratory droplets (called aerosols) produced when an infected person coughs, sneezes, breathes, or speaks. These droplets cause infections when they are inhaled or settle on mucous membranes, such as those that line the inside of the nose and mouth.

Humans are infected by the virus of SARs through respiratory droplets whose diameters range between 5-10 microns produced when an infected person coughs, sneezes, breathes, or speaks. Thus, the tiny droplets can spread over a meter away and remain in the environment for a long time.

On other hand, this epidemy is climate contamination because the virus is airborne and affects the breathing and health of humans on Earth. Besides, this epidemy has reduced much of the population. Furthermore, if the virus did indeed originate in a laboratory, then the objective of the virus is evident: control and reduction of the population due to a World Program of the elite (new world order: program 2030) and dark that control the humans on the Earth which is explained in the item of the severe Manipulation and Population Control in times of new world order & Tribulation.

In fact, it is very unlikely that the virus originated by consuming animals such as bats or pangolins when the Chinese have consumed these animals for centuries, which is recorded in their culture and without any consequence of epidemics. In addition, humanity has previously had plagues and epidemics such as the black plague and Spanish flu without such strict measures of control, confinement and restriction of human freedoms. In this way, it is surprising that on the eve of a scheduled plan for humanity (new world order: program 2030), strict confinement measures and restrictions were carried out.

Besides, it was also rumored that the virus was brought from the US to China at a military Olympics event in China with the objective possibly to cover up the origin of the virus. Subsequently, there were accusations between the two countries, China and the US, where China accused the US of producing AIDS in a laboratory to spread it around the world. From these accusations between these power countries and by simple logic, it is evident that the virus originated in a laboratory (regardless of which country it originated in). Because there are actually many virus laboratories in the power countries: China, US, Russia and some European countries, and these countries experiment with viruses very similar to SARS, it is very probable that the virus originated in a laboratory. In addition, there is the risk that a new virus will pass from the laboratory to a country or group in armed conflict on the Earth and in this way, the virus will spread in humans to cause human and destabilization and chaos on all the Earth.

In resume, the virus probably originated in a laboratory on the eve of an accelerated Program (new world order: program2030) by the dark desperate for control of the Earth which is happening in coincidence with the catastrophic climatic situation in the Earth and possible climatic signs of the Wrath of God [1] and very probably signs of the Tribulation (Mt. 24: 7).

Therefore, this is occurring in possible Tribulation times for bible believers who assure that in times of Tribulation biblical [1] prophecies must occur: pests (epidemic) (Mt. 24) and possible marking of humans (Ap.13:16) for the control of the dark.

Viruses from nature through the melting glaciers (Thawing glaciers): viruses hidden at the poles by the nature itself (God Allah!!) for times of Tribulation

In times of Tribulation, severe solar storms (possibly due to gravitational variations due to the entry of a big asteroid or Comet Planet in the solar system or a big asteroid or Comet Planet mentioned in the scriptures for times of Tribulation: Wormwood) will cause variations in the magnetic field lines, thus varying the solar radiation that reaches the Earth causing the melting of glaciers at the poles increasing the level of water in the oceans with subsequent consequences such as floods, tornadoes, droughts, non-uniform climate, and climate chaos. In addition, in these times of Tribulation, the increased in the melting of the glaciers at the poles (thawing of the glaciers at the poles) will cause the viruses hidden in the glaciers at the poles (mentioned in the bible for the Tribulation times Job 38-22) to pass into the oceans, from the oceans to the animals and the atmosphere, and from the animals and from the atmosphere to humans. These viruses are known as the viruses reserved for the times of Tribulation and the Wrath of the Eternal Allah!![1].

5.- Climate Change due to natural cyclical climate changes of the Earth affected by cyclical variations in the activity of the sun producing storms and sunspots which affects all the planets with the variation of their magnetic field lines varying the amount of solar radiation that enters the Earth: variation that is more evident due to the melting of glaciers at the poles, increasing the level of water in the oceans with subsequent consequences such as floods, tornadoes, droughts, severe and non-uniform climate, and climate chaos. The severe variations in the sun's cyclic activity can be explained by the large variations in nuclear and chemical reactions due to combustion that occurs within the sun, but what affects the combustion of the sun: the competition between fusion and chemical reaction and the gravitational force (gravitational pressure) due to the mass of the sun produces an imbalance in its functioning which can be increased by the gravitational waves produced by the instabilities of the planets of the solar system in their movement or by a big asteroid or invading Comet Planet to the solar system.

The passing natural cyclic phase of climatic change encountered in Earth's history is affected by the cyclic variations of the terrestrial magnetic field lines varying the amount of solar radiation that enters the Earth whose consequences are: Antarctica temperature change, melting glaciers in the north and south poles and increasing the level of water in the oceans, rise in sea level and rivers, simultaneous severe heat and severe cold in some parts of the Earth, severe flooding, storms and severe tornadoes, the proliferation of devastating hurricanes, forced migration of certain species of animals, desertification of fertile áreas, forest fires and droughts [6].

On other hand, the variation of the magnetic field lines is affected by the cyclic variations in the activity of the sun due to the storms, ejection of coronal mass of the sun, and sunspots, and the Earth has experienced cyclically every certain period. Besides, the unusual activity of the sun should also affect other planets as Jupiter and Mars for example. Moreover, the severe variations in the sun's cyclic activity with storms, ejection of coronal mass of the sun, and sunspots can be explained by the large variations in nuclear and chemical reactions due to the combustion that occurs within the sun. Furthermore, the variability in the combustion of the sun can be explained by the competition between fusion and chemical reaction and the gravitational force (gravitational pressure) due to the mass of the sun which produces an imbalance in its functioning which can be increased by the gravitational waves [2], [3] produced by the instabilities of the planets of the solar system in their movement or by a big asteroid or invading Comet Planet to the solar system which is explained in the next item.

6.- Climate Change due to the entrance of a big asteroid or Comet Planet to the solar system activating earthquakes and supervolcanoes and displacing many meteors and asteroids to the Earth and probably making the earth wobble: Comet Planet that with its gravitational and magnetic field also affects the sun which emits severe solar storms which affects the planets with the variation of their magnetic field lines, varying the amount of solar radiation that enters the Earth: variation that is more evident due to the melting of the glaciers at the poles, increasing the level of water in the oceans with subsequent consequences such as floods, tornadoes, droughts, severe and non-uniform climate and climate chaos: the same Comet Planet that is held responsible by some astronomers and scientists for biblical events (big earthquake in the Jesuchirst crucifixión, Noah's flood, destruction of Sodom and Gomorrah, opening of the sea by Moises when rescuing the Israelites from the Egyptians after the plagues of Egypt, opening of the sea by Josue in the Jordan Pass, motionless sun and moon for the large day of Joshua when Josue asked God Allah in the defeat of the amorites)

As it was mentioned before, the unusual variations in the activity of the Sun with the storms, ejection of coronal mass of the sun and sunspots is the reason for the variation of the magnetic field lines and small variations of the grades of the magnetic poles North and South varying the amount of solar radiation that enters the Earth which is the reasons of the severe climate catastrophes: Antarctica temperature change, melting glaciers in the north and south poles and increasing the level of water in the oceans, rise in sea level and rivers, severe and non-uniform climate and climate chaos, simultaneous severe heat and severe cold in some parts of the Earth, severe flooding, storms and severe tornadoes, the proliferation of devastating hurricanes, forced migration of certain species of animals, desertification of fertile áreas, forest fires and droughts [6].

In addition, the unusual activity of the sun should also affect other planets as Jupiter and Mars for example. However, the imbalance between fusion and chemical reaction and the gravitational force (gravitational pressure due to the mass of the sun) causes the variability in the combustion of the sun and the unusual activity of the sun (big storms, ejection of coronal mass of the sun and sunspots) and affects the large variations of magnetic field lines of the Earth can be explained by the gravitational waves [2], [3] produced by the instabilities of the planets of the solar system in their movement or by the entry of a big asteroid or the so-called big Comet Planet.

Then, the question is what is affecting the Sun activity in the last few years. In nature, nothing happens by chance and therefore and because it is a scientific article, it is necessary to explain the reason for the unusual activity of the sun by physics reasons. Indeed, the human being looks always for physical reasons to explain some natural phenomena but in the end, the reason for everything that happens on Earth is God Allah who controls everything in the Universe [1]. Then and explaining this scientifically, the probable reason for the increase or decrease of the fuel of the combustion process and the variations of the nuclear and chemical reactions in the sun and the imbalance of it with the gravitation force of the sun mass which produces storms, ejection of coronal mass of the sun and severe sunspots which affects the magnetic field lines of the Earth is due to gravitational variations in the proximity of the sun [2], [3]. On other hand, slight gravitational variations in the proximity of the sun can be produced due to instabilities in the movement of the planets of the solar system or small asteroids that pass near the sun and that can affect the sun by gravitational waves that reach the sun. However, the reason for big storms, ejection of coronal mass of the sun and sunspots that have occurred in the sun, and the large variations of magnetic field lines of the Earth can be explained by the entry of a big asteroid or the big Comet Planet which affects from afar with its gravitational and magnetic field to the sun and all the planets of the solar system. According to some research astronomers of the Comet Planet, it has a cycle of movement in its passage through the solar system and three velocities.

Besides, the Earth is experiencing the severe climatic change mentioned before combined with catastrophic situations, for example, the increase in the activation of many volcanoes and supervolcanoes, the formation of sinkholes, the increase in earthquakes, and increased sightings of meteorites and asteroids entering the Earth with some asteroids passing nearby of the Earth. On other hand, the number of meteorites and asteroids passing near or enter to the Earth and the activation of supervolcanoes and the increase of earthquakes have increased in the last few years. Therefore, the question is which is the reason for the increased activation of supervolcanoes, a severe increase of earthquakes, and the number of meteorites and asteroids passing near or enter to the Earth in the last years.

The unusual activity of the sun can explain the global warming of the Earth, severe climate catastrophes mentioned before, the affectation of the magnetic field lines of the Earth, and the climate change in other planets such as Mars and Jupiter for example. Nevertheless, the unusual activity of the sun can not explain the entrance of many meteorites to the Earth, the increase in earthquakes, and the increase in the activation of supervolcanoes on Earth. Then, it makes us think that all the severe climatic changes and the catastrophic situations on the Earth are connected and that, there is an outer reason that is affecting the sun, the Earth, and other planets such as Mars or Jupiter and possibly changing the orbit of the planets around the sun. Also, this outer reason is displacing many meteorites and asteroids to the Earth, activating many volcanoes on the Earth, and increasing earthquakes.

Therefore, the logical reason is that a big asteroid or a Comet Planet coming from the cosmos has entered our solar system. This Comet Planet is actually commented on by many astronomers and respectable scientists. Then, this Comet Planet is already affecting from afar at its entrance to our solar system with its gravitational and magnetic field to the planets of our solar system and the sun. Then, nothing is possible to do regarding severe climate change

and the chaos on the Earth, it is out of our control of us. It is not possible to control a big asteroid or Comet Planet in the solar system and worse if this is related to the Wrath and Judgments of God [1].

Actually, many scientists and astronomers attribute the reason to a big asteroid or big asteroids and meteorites pushed by the passage of a big Comet Planet entering the solar system for some catastrophes that have occurred on the Earth. Therefore, the same scientists (who do not want to admit the existence of God) have explained certain biblical facts mentioned before through the passage of this Comet Planet: big earthquake in the Jesuchrist crucifixión (Mt. 27:51) [1], Noah's flood (Gen. 7) [1], destruction of Sodom and Gomorrah (Gen. 19) [1], the opening of the sea by Moises when rescuing the Israelites from the Egyptians after the plagues of Egypt (Exod.14), three days darkness in the plagues of egypt (Exod. 10:21), the opening of the sea by Josue in the Jordan Pass (Josu. 3), motionless sun and moon for the large day of Joshua when Josue asked God Allah in the defeat of the amorites (Josu. 10), fire on Job's cattle (Job 1:16), the shadow of hezekiah and Earth tilted: tilt of the earth's axis (2 Rey. 20:11), famine and droughts in the time of Joseph of Egypt (Gen. 41:54), famine and droughts in the time of David and Saul (2 Sam. 21), famine and droughts in the time of Ruth (Ruth 1) [1]. Also, some scientists attribute the disappearance of dinosaurs and some species of animals to the passage of this Comet Planet. Indeed, this Comet Planet has been documented in Chinese (Supernova Chinese Star 1054) and European (picture Hamburg Germany 1697) literature and for the collapse of Mayans because this has entered the solar system in the past due to its cycle of movement in the cosmos.

Actually, astronomical organizations will not report probably the entry of this Comet Planet into the solar system until it is seen by humans in the skies of the Earth. Thus, the question is how humans could know that the Comet Planet has entered the solar system?

Humans will be able to realize that this Comet Planet has entered the solar system due to the catastrophic effects in the climate mentioned above that are already occurring on the Earth and mainly due to the severe activation of volcanoes and earthquakes and the continuous and increase of the sighting of meteorites and asteroids which are pushed by the Comet Planet and possibly with the variation of the orbit of the Earth.

After all these events, the Comet Planet will be visible in the skies of the earth but with consequences on the Earth worse than in its entry into the solar system: possible wobble of the earth and possible inversion of magnetic poles and in the worst case possible inversión of poles terrestrial which is an apocalypse described in the Bible for the times of Tribulation and the Wrath of God [1].

7.- Severe climate change due to the Arm of God Allah thus also explaining all the above reasons being more evident in times of Tribulation and the Wrath of God!!

Life on the Earth is possible because of the mercy of God [1] and explained scientifically because we are in a living zone (not so hot, not so cold) in the way of the Earth around the Sun: the Earth is located in the third position concerning the other planets [7]. But if any perturbation occurs for example any gravitational and magnetic disturbances [2], [3] caused by the passage of a big asteroid or the Comet Planet, then things and the climate on the Earth can change easily.

In addition and as it was mentioned before, some scientists and scientific organizations (NASA) (who do not want to admit the existence of God) have explained certain biblical facts [1] mentioned before through the passage of the Comet Planet: big earthquake in the Jesuchrist crucifixión (Mt. 27:51), Noah's flood (Gen. 7), destruction of Sodom and Gomorrah (Gen. 19), opening of the sea by Moises when rescuing the Israelites from the Egyptians after the plagues of Egypt (Exod. 14), three days darkness in the plagues of egypt (Exod. 10:21), opening of the sea by Josue in the Jordan Pass (Josu. 3), motionless sun and moon for the large day of Joshua when Josue asked God Allah in the defeat of the amorites (Josu. 10), fire on Job's cattle (Job 1:16), shadow of hezekiah and Earth tilted: tilt of the earth's axis (2 Rey. 20:11), famine and droughts in the time of Joseph of Egypt (Gen. 41:54), famine and droughts in the time of David and Saul (2 Sam. 21), famine and droughts in the time of Ruth (Ruth 1).

Besides, some scientists attribute the disappearance of dinosaurs and some species of animals to the passage of this Comet Planet.

Nevertheless, according to some astronomers and erudite in religion, this Comet Planet or the big asteroid that it pushes is the same one that is mentioned in the Apocalypse and is called Wormwood (Apoc. 8:11) [1].

Furthermore, research astronomers of this Comet Planet also state that this has three velocities where the third velocity is the most terrifying. If this is so and due to the biblical records of the passage of this Comet Planet said by the same scientists to explain bible facts, this Comet Planet appears according to certain events that occur on the Earth and its speed is increased according to the acceleration of events in the Earth guided by the Arm of God [1].

Therefore, there is a connection with the Arm of God of the catastrophes and miracles mentioned before which are explained by scientists with the Comet Planet.

Nevertheless and actually, most astronomers and astronomical organizations (NASA) deny the possible existence of this Comet Planet or that this Comet Planet has entered our solar system and passed close to Earth in the past (probably to avoid mentioning the asteroids of the time of Tribulation and of the Wrath of God that is mentioned in the Bible and not to create panic and to have the control the humans until the last circumstances of a catastrophe in the Earth due to the passage of a big asteroid or Comet Planet). But, the idea of this Comet Planet that may already be causing severe climatic effects on the Earth from far comes from the same scientists for denying the existence of God and to explain biblical facts of the past through this Comet Planet as it was mentioned before.

Therefore, in the past, scientists accept that this Comet Planet has passed a few times in the solar system, and actually, scientists say that this Comet Planet does not exist.

In this way, humans should not believe everything said by these scientific organizations that explain what occurs in the cosmos (NASA) because they contradict themselves in their information or report what is convenient for them.

Also, human beings must not believe everything said by organizations and individuals who control the Earth because they obey directions imposed by the dark and the elite within the matrix triangle of control of the Earth.

In addition, it should not be surprising that they contradict each other concerning the Comet Planet, because this is related to the Wrath and Judgments of God [1].

Most of these scientific organizations do not admit that God exists, even though they know that God exists but they don't want to admit or mention it.

Besides, those scientific organizations try not to mention God not to inspire humans who can reach full knowledge of God and be similar to God because in the biblical scriptures it is mentioned: The man is made in the image and likeness of God [1].

There are many examples of humans in the biblical scriptures who, having the full knowledge of God, managed to obtain the spirit and power of God and demonstrated it by performing acts that are not possible for humans and that are considered miracles. Examples of these humans mentioned in the biblical scriptures are Moses with the Rod of God, Elijah, Daniel, Joshue, Enoch and the same Envoy of God made man Jesus Christ [1].

Then, the reason for these organizations to hide important facts and realities and present to humanity those that suit them is evident: to have control of humans on Earth.

However, many of the dark and the elite that controls the Earth have built many bunkers in New Zealand and other countries. The question is if this is due to some event that they already know will occur on the Earth which is not communicated to humanity and probably is the passage of this Comet Planet related to the Wrath of God [1].

Besides, many films and documentaries have been made recently about a big asteroid passing near or entering the Earth or cosmic catastrophes which is also surprising because of the catastrophic climatic situation of the Earth in actuality.

In addition, important magazines (The Economist) directed by the dark and the elite have published on their covers climatic and cosmic catastrophes related to the sun or asteroids. Actually, the Earth is going through an unprecedented climate crisis in coincidence with the publication of these magazines and movies and with the risk of nuclear war and still in the epidemic situation and with a program for humans of a new world order or program 2030 and possibly in principles of Tribulation.

In addition, this should not be surprising that the organizations that are concerned about climate change (ONU) try to make human beings believe that the reason for severe climate change on the Earth is due to the contamination of gases by CO₂ and that human beings can control it.

In nature, nothing happens by chance and therefore and because it is a scientific article, it was necessary to explain by physics reasons the reason for the catastrophes and miracles before mentioned and the unusual activity of the sun affecting the variation of the magnetic field lines of the Earth which affects the climate in the Earth mentioned in the last items.

Indeed, the human being looks always for physical reasons to explain some natural phenomena but in the end, the reason for everything that happens on Earth is God Allah who controls everything in the Universe and the climate as the facts mentioned in the bible [1] and that scientists explain it with the Comet Planet.

Then and in times of Tribulation [1], the Comet Planet or the big asteroid that it pushes is the same one that is mentioned in the Apocalypse and is called Wormwood will cause catastrophes climatic (severe climate change and

climate chaos), activation of many volcanoes and supervolcanoes, formation of sinkholes, increase of earthquake and besides increased sightings of meteorites and asteroids entering the Earth with some asteroids passing nearby of the Earth and apocalyptic catastrophes (possible wobble of the earth, possible inversion of magnetic poles and in the worst case possible inversión of poles terrestrial and variation of the orbit of the Earth) mentioned before, which is an apocalypse described in the Bible for the times of Tribulation and the Wrath of God [1]: the sun will darken and the moon will not shine (Mt. 24:29, Apoc. 6:12).

In addition and as was mentioned before, the increase in the melting of the poles will cause the viruses that are hidden in the poles (mentioned in the bible for the Tribulation times Job 38-22) to pass into the oceans, from the oceans to the animals and the atmosphere, and from the animals and from the atmosphere to humans. These viruses are known as the viruses reserved for the times of Tribulation and the Wrath of the Eternal Allah!! [1].

According to some astronomers and erudite in religion, they mention that the constellation of the stars of 2017 forming the woman with the moon under her feet is probably the one mentioned in the apocalypse [1]: the woman and the dragón (Apoc. 12).

Then, it is a coincidence with some erudite in religion that has already started the labor pains on the Earth (Mt. 24: 8). If this is so, this is very probable that the Comet Planet has entered the solar system and it is affecting already from afar with climatic catastrophes to the planets of the solar system.

Besides, this is necessary and essential for the Intervention of the Superior Entity (God Allah: For the love of myself and my chosen ones) in times of Tribulation [1] at the time timely due to everything mentioned in this document and that humans know regarding the increase of inequity, discord and evil among humans.

This Intervention of the Superior Entity Allah is mentioned in the biblical scriptures [1] with the opening of seals (Apoc. 6) and trumpets (Apoc. 8:6) and with the full manifestation of the Lamb of God (Apoc. 5) and the sealed (Apoc. 7) chosen for the illumination and awakening of the Eternal's chosen people guided and taken to the New City of God: The New Jerusalem: New Heavens and New Earth (Apoc. 21)!!!.

Severe Manipulation and Population Control in times of new world order & Tribulation

The dark and the elite control human life in different forms which is evident to most humans living on the Earth who are aware of the methods of control and manipulation.

Population control is through systematic methods of persuasive manipulation and indoctrination with networks and technological devices and even with some human zombies in service of the dark and the elite.

Therefore, this intervention in the population of the elites and the dark that control humans on the Earth is due to the state of numbness of many human beings: a state of numbness or hypnosis of the population that does not allow them to see and understand the situation in which their lives and those of others unfold. The responsible for this condition are great powers (in politics, economics, and religion), controlling and directing the destiny of thousands or perhaps more than thousands of people. Besides, some countries are controlled by the power structure (religion or military): there are communist and dictatorial totalitarian countries in similar conditions of population control

or even worse, where all those powers (in politics, economics, and religion) are in a single power: the military or the religion.

Therefore, these great powers (in politics, economics, and religion) influence humans through their mass media of public disclosure and their systematic methods of persuasive indoctrination and continuous manipulation leading them to a sleeping condition without much resistance.

Fortunately, many of those sleeping humans have woken up and have been able to see the Light of the Awakening of Consciousness sent by the Superior and Eternal Entity Allah [1]: Light that is sent by the Superior Entity to the human beings that want to see its Light and within the Sound of Silence. In this way, many human beings have managed to see the naked Light without being persuaded or deceived by the powers that control the Earth. Then, they can see and understand many things that they did not know before.

Unfortunately, many humans have been able to see the naked Light sent by the Superior and Eternal Entity Allah: speak without speaking, listen without hearing, and write songs that are never shared. These are the humans who have already awakened but who do not dare to disturb the Sound of Silence and communicate to the Earth and the rest of human beings the Light of the Awakening of Consciousness that they have already seen.

The Sound of Silence means the censorship directed from the power structure in politics, economics, and religion that silences freedom of expression and kidnaps the TRUTH: TRUTH that is the only one that in front of EVERYONE can contradict the dark that controls the humans in the Earth, deny them and reveal their dark intentions. However, there is Sound in the Sound of Silence, because some words are allowed to be pronounced, but those that are convenient for the elite and the dark and those that allow the demagoguery of power. But, it is also at the same time a silence, because those words do not express anything of the truth and do not communicate the Light of the Awakening of Consciousness to the rest of human beings. Therefore, the human being preferred to enslave himself and worship that condition of numbness, hypnosis, and silence.

Therefore, I write this scientific article to achieve the awakening of all humans so that all humans can see the Light of the Awakening of Consciousness sent by the Superior Entity Allah to those who want to see its Light within the Sound of Silence until the voice of the same Eternal is heard energetically throughout the Earth in times of Tribulation and the Wrath of God: a voice that the Biblical Prophets already heard within the Sound of Silence and written in the Bible Koran Torah inspired by the same Supreme Being and Creator God Allah!! [1].

In this way, it is concluded that this power structure (in politics, economics, and religion) together with the organizations (ONU OEA BM FMI OIT OMS Vatican and developed countries that print additional money at convenience inclusive to use for countries at war causing imbalance and global economic crisis) and multinationals, enterprises, educational institutions controlled by the elite and dark are ineffective and with mediocre results in terms of reducing inequity and poverty in the Earth. This should not be surprising for the human beings that inhabit the Earth, because it is evident that this power structure is interested in controlling the population, favoring themselves and those humans that allow this control with inequity without caring about the human beings who have been reduced to poverty and inequity for not following the guideline of the matrix triangle of control of the politicians that rule the country and dark and elite that controls humans in the Earth. Thus, the

phrase reducing inequity is a false argument and a farce used by politicians to come to power in their respective countries.

In this form, it is deplorable that many politicians who come to power in their countries obey the guidelines of powerful countries or the dark that control humans on the Earth and do not worry about reducing the inequity of their citizens in their countries. Thus, it is lamentable that this power structure (in politics, economics, and religion) and the rulers (governing) of the respective countries with this power structure (in politics, economics, and religion) do not follow the guideline and example given by the Envoy of God Jesus Christ [1] with which it is possible to govern and achieve coexistence and harmony between human beings without inequity which is summarized in a message: Love your brother (all humans beings) as yourself!! (Mt.22-39).

Furthermore, this is also lamentable the passive role of religion who knows about it and covers up this ineffective power structure that does not reduce the inequity on the Earth for approximately 2000 years after the coming of the Envoy of God: Jesus Christ [1]. Therefore, religion is complicit in the actual situation on the Earth, which is in wars, conflicts, and full of discord and evil, which has diminished the love between humans on the Earth (Mt. 24-12).

Therefore, it is important to make evident, detail, and specify the forms of control and manipulation with which the dark and the elite that controls the Earth interfere in human life:

- **by increasing taxes** with any possible excuse to exhaust humans and mainly the middle class for the benefit of a happy few who get rich. Therefore, it increased the gap between classes (poor and rich) increasing poverty and inequity.

- **through armed conflicts and wars** between countries where the power countries (which consider and call themselves developed) create discord, wars, and chaos between countries (often bordering countries with the same origins and with the same culture: Russia and Ukraine: war motivated by US OTAN EU) with obvious objectives:

- to later usurp its resources (oil energy resource: US Iraq Kuwait)

- to later control them politically and economically (US Iraq Kuwait). Nevertheless, when these power or developed countries (as they call themselves) cannot control or usurp their resources, they begin to block them economically (Russia in the war between Russia and Ukraine where developed countries influence the war by printing additional money to use for the war causing imbalance and global economic crisis instead of looking for ways to avoid it). Therefore, the countries blocked (Cuba Venezuela Nicaragua Russia China North Korea Iran) caused chaos and economic crisis with the knowledge and complicity of the world organizations responsible (ONU OEA BM FMI OIT OMS Vatican) and make the population believe that the cause of the economic crisis is the government in power. However, some countries have resisted these blockades (Cuba Venezuela Nicaragua Russia China North Korea Iran) and managed to show that it is possible to have governments independent of the control of these powers or countries that believe they own the Earth.

- to put rulers (governing) of interest in the countries in conflict (US Irak Kuwait).

- to control them using the pretext of placing military bases in the countries in conflict (NATO OTAN: military bases in some European countries, US military bases: in some South American countries, and in some countries of

Europe). In addition, this is preferable to reduce military bases in other countries and reduce nuclear weapons, and use the financial resources for the reduction of inequity and poverty on the Earth. Thus, the organizations responsible for the proliferation of nuclear weapons (OIEA) have played an ineffective and passive (cover-up) role, which has caused the risk of a third nuclear world war to be imminent.

Therefore, the best thing is to have good relations with all the countries of the Earth which are again summed in the Bible [1] in a message: Love your brother (all human beings) as yourself! (Mt.22-39). Thus, it is possible to reduce the economic resources for nuclear weapons which can be used to reduce poverty and inequity among human beings.

- **through the war against terror** where the power countries (which consider and call themselves developed) allocate a large number of resources and money to the war against terror that can be used to reduce poverty and inequity on the Earth and increase fairness in the humans. However and actually, this is a false speech used to point to countries that oppose the control or directive of the powers and that have a culture, religion (Iran Palestine), or political structure different from that of the powers and later make conflict and war to later control them or usurp their resources (some Arab and Muslim countries for example: EEUU: Irak, Libyan and blaming an entire country for terrorism and occupying for years (Afganistán)). In this way and actually, some countries have developed nuclear weapons (North Korea, Iran) to protect themselves in some way, and thus, the same thing does not happen to them as to the countries mentioned above (Irak, Libyan) and that have been destroyed with the false discourse of the war against terror or of extremist religion. In this way, the best thing is to have good relations with all the countries of the Earth which are again summed in the Bible [1] in a message: Love your brother (all human beings) as yourself! (Mt.22-39) (and not to go around the Earth pointing out terrorists to any country that opposes its guidelines). Therefore, it is possible to reduce the economic resources for the war against terror which can be used to reduce poverty and inequity among human beings.

- **through the war against drugs** where a large number of resources and money are also allocated that can also be used to reduce poverty and inequity on the Earth and increase equity in humans. In addition, there are many other substances and products consumed by humans that can be harmful to health and that are allowed and have not become a vice (it corroborates that when something is forbidden, this increases the interest in obtaining it which is explained from the beginning of creation in Genesis [1]: an apple from the tree of good and evil in the garden of Eden: Adam and Eve). In addition, many countries have allowed the use of certain types of drugs for medical purposes (Uruguay, Bolivia) where the drug use has gone unnoticed in these countries. Then, it is preferable to use the resources and money from the war against drugs for the reduction of inequity and poverty on Earth.

- **through religion:** where the control of the population through institutions of religion and organizations (Vatican) has happened since the times of the Envoy of God Jesus Christ (when the scribes and Pharisees reproached Jesus Christ for following the guideline of God which was contradictorily and surprisingly opposed for the religion of that time and indeed, the same religion was the main responsible (Jewish scribes and Pharisees) for his crucifixion) until now with a structure of religion that tries to control the population through a guideline and speeches that obey the Vatican and the actual governments of each country (which is evident when there are countries such as

Nicaragua that do not follow a guideline of the church and the elite and then, the religion surprisingly actively intervenes in politics).

Besides, the institutions and organizations of religion (Vatican) are the main ones responsible for the increase in the gap between classes (poor and rich) and inequity among human beings due to the passive attitude in their participation against the hidden powers on the Earth for approximately 2000 years after of the coming of the Envoy of God Jesus Christ [1].

In addition, this same passive attitude of religion through its repetitive and passive sermons (very different from the guideline given by the envoy of God Jesus Christ [1]: Jn. 13, Mt. 10, 34 Mt. 21, 13 who already recriminated them (Scribes and Pharisees) approximately 2000 years ago: Mt. 23) contributes to the state of numbness or hypnosis of the population that does not allow humans to see the Light of Awakening and understand the situation in which their lives are governed and controlled by hidden powers in their lives. Possibly, this is also one of the objectives of religion: to contribute to this state of hypnosis in humans so that they do not wake up and in this way, the control of the matrix is effective throughout the Earth employing the political and economic powers of the respective countries.

However, when it is of interest or when the situation of political power in a country is not following the matrix or with the powers that control underdeveloped countries, religion surprisingly intervenes in politics, even giving political speeches (Nicaragua and in other countries of South America). In this way, this confirms that religion intervenes actively in human life at its convenience and when it is of interest or when they are forced to intervene by the dark and the elite.

Besides, it is deplorable the increase in abortions with possible damage to the organism of women (threads, cervix) who abort without knowledge of the medical personnel (false medical negligence with breach of the medical oath of the use of Medicine for human good) and the religión of the possible experimentation and use of active substances of the embryos by the dark.

It is well known that despite criticism of the cloning of sheep Dolly (soulless cloning) because it is against the principles of creation of the human being (consisting of the soul) by God, scientists have continued to intervene in subjects that belong and compete to God and worse still with embryos without there having been a strong claim by the religion that is principally responsible for defending the Creation of God.

Then, this is contradictory and lamentable that the religión does not intervene in a similar way to that of Jesus Christ [1] (active and energetic) for the defense of the Earth in the war of good against evil and against the dark powers that constantly generate conflicts, discord, inequity and evil in the Earth.

In this form, the conclusion reached and to which many humans have reached is that religion is a power most actually used (along with political and economic power) by the elite and the dark for the control of humans on Earth.

- through political power using the false argument used by politicians to reduce inequity and poverty where a large number of resources and money have been allocated to the political powers and rulers (governing) of many

countries for centuries by the respective organizations responsible (FMI BM) without any results and in many countries, poverty and inequity have increased. In this way, this leads us to think that resources and money are destined to specific humans or selected groups that contribute to the control of the matrix in the Earth and redistribute the money and resources at their convenience and interest. Besides, the bureaucracy is a structure of order and rules of management and administration used within the governments of each country that contribute to the inefficiency and manipulation of the required procedures in human life that ultimately affect the life of each human being when they require formalities that end up being complicated and time-consuming. Thus, this power structure in politics, economics and religion for the control of the population is ineffective and obeys the interests of the dark who control the humans on the Earth, and is used ineffectively by the rulers (governing) of the countries who come to power precisely with the false discourse of reducing poverty and inequity.

- **through the pretext of climate change** where a large number of resources and money are allocated for so-called climate change that can be used to reduce poverty and inequity on the Earth and increase equity in humans. The warming of the atmosphere by the increase in carbon dioxide CO₂ gases and the greenhouse effect due to the consumption by industries and factories is increasing but still, it contributes with a small percentage to climate change.

Nevertheless, it is very important to diminish this percentage of warming of the atmosphere by CO₂ gases as much we can but because of reasons of consideration and respect for nature and the Creation of God [1].

Other reasons contribute with more percentage to the severe climate change because there are droughts with increases in temperatures in some places of the Earth where there is not much climate pollution by gases.

Severe climate change is frequently due to solar storms and variations in the magnetic field lines of the Earth because of gravitational variations in the solar system or due to the entry of an asteroid or Comet Planet which is controlled and allá Universe by God.

In addition, the technology can also be used to generate climate chaos and even earthquakes and destabilize a country. The important question is: is it possible to change and make any chaotic effect on the climate with the actual technology to create chaos or destabilize a country?

Actually, it is known that there is the possibility of human intervention in the climate using technology for different reasons: positive or negative and then, climate change is a climate scam. For example: Storm Gloria hit Catalonia, was it a punishment from nature itself? or was it a coincidence of nature? (apparent coincidence because everything and nature is effectively controlled by the Eternal) or by some technology that can affect the climate?

Actually, there is a strong rumor of the existence of the possibility of changing the climate by means of Meteorological Weapons: Antennas of high-intensity radio waves to change the climate with the possibility of inducing rains, hurricanes, and the possible induction of earthquakes: Haarp Antennas (American Technology) & Sura Antennas (Russian Technology).

Thus, there is also the rumor of the possible induction of earthquakes in some countries with this technology to destabilize them and create chaos or for other dark reasons (one of these strong rumors is the earthquake in Haiti).

Therefore, this technology can be used as a climate weapon which is terrible for humans living on the Earth: simple humans inside a country affected by an earthquake or severe climate change think that it is a natural cause without knowing that this is due to the climate technology used to destabilize a country and create chaos!!

This is actually known from some countries that bombard clouds to generate rain to improve agriculture. Therefore, this is possible with the actual technology to affect the climate to generate rain or change the climate conditions for a positive reason. In fact, there is also a country that is trying to create an artificial sun by means of a nuclear fusion reactor, but without success in terms of its application and with considerable risk to nature and human beings.

Therefore, this concludes that it is not possible to try to imitate the Eternal in the creation of the main star of the Earth: the Sun that illuminates humans daily and that moreover, illuminates with mercy because it illuminates all good and bad humans [1].

Therefore, if it is not considered climate change due to the possible use of technology by power countries to create climatic chaos, natural climate change is mainly due to solar storms and variations of the Earth's magnetic field lines because of gravitational variations in the solar system or due to the entry of an asteroid or Comet Planet what is controlled and all the Universe by God. Natural climate change is not due to the emission of CO₂ and the greenhouse effect. Thus, severe climate change due to the emission of CO₂ and the greenhouse effect is a complete fallacy.

Obviously, the world organizations involved with the climate (ONU) try to make humanity believe that the emission of CO₂ and the greenhouse effect is the reason for the severe climatic changes that human being has experienced on the Earth to receive economic resources and funding to avoid mentioning the Omnipotence of God [1] in the control of the Earth and the climate.

Therefore, human beings must not believe everything said by the organizations and individuals that control this Earth and that obey the directions imposed within the matrix triangle of control of the Earth.

Indeed, climate change is controlled by the Eternal God (which is explained in the Bible with a lot of examples with Moses, Josue, and Hezekiah) and thus, this is better to use the resources and money allocated to these climate organizations for the so-called climate change to reduce poverty in the Earth and increase equity in humans.

- through the sport by means of the persuasive manipulation of observers or attendees at sporting events through commercials programs, commentators (hidden words and numbers in speech), and players participating in the match: with gestures or sequences of plays, numbers, words, or details in the players uniform, referees (make decision of plays in favor of a team purposely: false bad arbitration) or leading organizers committing sports corruption not applying the rules or discriminating players (Serbian, Russian and Belarusian tennis players at tennis competitions due to some tennis organizations) or teams (Russian sports clubs and inclusive the Russian national team due to FIFA decision) at convenience.

In addition, sports championship organizations commit sports corruption by making play players of a country team who are not citizens of the respective countries through local and even international sports championships (which has been much commented and debated in South America and international championships, including the FIFA).

This is corroborated that it is so because later the disciplinary committee (TAS) of the organizing body (FIFA) fines the player who has played and the country's team recognizes that an act of sports corruption has been carried out (passing off as a citizen of a country to which it is not through a sports championship). Therefore, the organization is complicit in the act of sports corruption because it does not apply the respective rules when the main rule has been breached, which is that the teams must play with citizens of their own countries.

It is surprising that this occurs because many country teams nationalize players and in this way, they can play for their teams without the inconvenience and thus avoid this act of sports corruption.

Then, the teams of amateur championships and collegiate leagues and championships learn these same artifices of corruption by failing to comply with sports regulations by having players play in their championships who are not affiliated with the respective sports team or the respective collegiate leagues or who have not studied at the respective college or institution (making collegiate or member of an institution or college who is not through a sports championship).

In this way, the members of the organizing and disciplinary committee must apply the regulations so that these acts of sports corruption do not occur and a precedent is formed so that the other teams, institutions, collegiate leagues, colleges and even national teams do not do the same.

The control and manipulation of the population through the sport are more evident when there are countries in conflict or war: instead of uniting the countries in conflict by means of the sport, the respective organizations (FIFA UEFA) discriminate and increase the conflict!!

Besides, this is important to mention the control of the dark and the elite in the new world order in sports as for example Tennis and Football discriminating and not allowing the participation of tennis players (including top tennis players), Football Countries and Sport Clubs in international competitions for reasons of restrictions due to the epidemic, conflict or war (including countries that organized previous World Cups: Russia) where the interest, quality, and love for this sport have increased and that must be used to unite human beings and countries and not to allow them to participate: which increases the division and conflict between countries or humans).

This is important to highlight and value the position of the ATP in deciding that the ATP does not agree that athletes from certain countries (Russia and Belarus) cannot participate in international tournaments stating that this is against the principles of merit and non-discrimination. In this way, the ATP decided not to recognize some tennis tournaments such as the Wimbledon tournament.

On another hand, this is tremendously criticizable that the organization responsible for Football (FIFA UEFA) participates in armed conflicts or wars with discriminatory decisions in Football, increasing the war by not allowing countries in conflict to participate in the World Cup of Football.

In this way, the FIFA slogan of no to racism and some form of discrimination is a complete farce and used for convenience and interest (in the same style as all the other organizations: mainly ONU, OEA, OMS, FMI, BM, VATICAN that control humans and that in 2000 years of the coming of the Envoy of God have not been able to solve iniquity and poverty), discrimination that has been evident in the conflict between Russia and Ukraine.

Football is the main sport on the Earth and it is the one that can unite human beings the most and should be used as a source of union and not division!!

- **through education** where this is used by many countries to induce and manipulate their inhabitants in a certain political direction through the dissemination of knowledge and even the textbooks of the students. In addition, this is objectionable that many underdeveloped countries come to power with the false discourse of reducing illiteracy and improving education in the country.

Thus, many underdeveloped countries have increased illiteracy and education has been degraded because this favors the politicians of the country's government: having ignorant people who do not see what they do with the country's money and who cannot criticize them.

This is unfortunate because education is what allows progress and improvement in all aspects of the country: The greatness of people depends on the education that gives the independence of individuals who are the ones that make the country advance.

- **through world organizations to control countries: ONU, OEA, OMS, Vatican, OTAN, UE:** in this way, many countries have to obey the guidelines of these organizations, which often do not respond to the needs of the citizens of each country.

In addition, many institutions in the countries must obey the organizations (for example the Vatican for the congregation and priests of the catholic religion) in a rigid way, which is often not in accordance with the situation of the country's citizens, who often need new variants or guidelines.

Indeed, some organizations can cause chaos, conflict or war for example the war between Russia with Ucraina where the possible annexation of Ucraina to the OTAN and UE is one of the reasons for the war between these two countries (manifested also by the Vatican).

Therefore, there would be no war between these two countries without those organizations. In this way, the money allocated due to some of these ineffective organizations can be used to reduce inequity and poverty on the Earth.

- **through world organizations of spionage (CIA, FBI, KGB, Gestapo, SS):** by means of the persuasive interference in the countries and rulers of some underdeveloped countries (some South America and Center America countries and some European, Asia and African countries) with the objective of the powerful countries of control, manipulate or destabilize countries and inclusive simple humans (by means of the personal data of thousands of people around the world).

It is very probable that these espionage organizations make these interferences and espionage even in simple humans. Then, this is very probable that these organizations work for the dark and the elite and that, in addition, they have among their tasks or responsibilities to investigate the presence of God-like human on Earth (in the same style as Jesus Christ).

Normally, the individuals who work for these organizations go unnoticed by working in diplomatic positions or ordinary jobs without being detected.

However, simple humans within underdeveloped countries do not even imagine that these individuals are in their infiltrated countries informing and following the directions of the powerful countries. Besides, they are the initiating sources (hidden) of destabilizing demonstrations and protests in underdeveloped countries.

This is unfortunate that the military of underdeveloped countries (which obviously have knowledge of these organizations of spionage) allow the infiltration of these organizations in their countries.

In addition, it is surprising that when other humans or research groups (Wikileaks: who publish news leaks and classified media provided by anonymous sources) do the same as these organizations, the powerful countries get upset and begin to persecute them and even put them in prison (Assange).

Then, the powerful countries believe they have so much power on the Earth that they can put infiltrate individuals on the Earth to spy on countries, but humans or anonymous groups (Wikileaks) cannot do the same thing to these powerful countries.

This is not in accordance with the guidelines and message of the envoy of God Jesus Christ (Mt. 7-4). In addition, when individuals who work for these organizations rebel and leave their organizations, they are persecuted (Snowden: from the US to Russia) because those organizations do not want that forms of espionage, control and manipulation of the population and simple humans to be disclosed to the rest of humans in the Earth.

Therefore, it is very important to mention that the countries do not need infiltration of these organizations or military bases of other countries (OTAN US), this is enough with their own military and with their own people.

Besides, it is important to make evident, detail and specify the methods and devices used by the dark and the elite for the control and manipulation of the population with the Severe Universal Big Brother Program for the control and manipulation of humans in the eve of a program of new world order (program 2030) and possibly of Tribulation.

Severe Universal Big Brother Program for the control of humans with surveillance programs with technological devices (surveillance cameras) and with mind reading (telepathy) and thought induction from possible liquid and solid chips introduced into the human being

- Control and manipulation have been made on the Earth since its beginning by means of systematic methods of persuasive manipulation and indoctrination used by some zombie humans and the dark who contribute to the manipulation and induction to the concupiscence of the humans and Nazarenes.

- Manipulation and induction to the concupiscence of the dark and elite through the subjugation of employees and humans by enterprises or by dark groups so that employees or humans make manipulation games with details (investing work time to play like children) receiving bribes or labor benefits or with possible retaliation if they do not obey. Nevertheless and actually, it is criticizable the use of inclusive children to manipulate and to teach them to manipulate in the same style as zombies.

- Coincidence games, activities, plans and events programmed in sequence (inclusive pyrotechnic sounds in sequence), covert numbers and covert words (in identification documents, cards, car plates, devices used by

humans), encrypted, hidden codes or small phrases and numbers not visible to the naked eye concealed in objects, covert words in the speech of zombie humans and from multimedia and channels of traditional digital technological devices through movies, programs and even newscasts to manipulate and induce concupiscence in the life of human beings and Nazarenes and inclusive to speak in code with the humans who know the surveillance programs and worst using in those channels and programs derogatory words with the Nazarenes (in the style of Nazism with the Jews) in the complicity of close acquaintances, zombies and dark who participate profiting from the system for the vile metal and contribute to the persecution of Nazarenes in times of Tribulation and new world order.

- Control, manipulation and tracing programs with all technological devices actually used by most humans. In addition, the control, manipulation and tracing are carried out through the same data entered in the networks that serve for the control of humans by the dark. This is important to mention even that the same software of the technological devices keeps track of the information that is entered or heard or seen to later send specific information of what has been entered, heard or seen (for example some human beings mention or talk near a technological device on pain in the body and later surprisingly information on medications or treatments for the respective pain appears).

- Control and surveillance programs in living and working places are also by means of covert technological cameras and possibly with infrared cameras (some humans have identified the covert traditional technological cameras due to the continuous clicking sounds in the devices with examples as covert device discovered in Ecuador Consulate in Assange's asylum and the covert devices discovered in some Presidential Houses as the Carondelet Palace in Ecuador). Besides, the covert technological cameras are possibly covertly installed in technological and digital devices, technological processors used to process data and in the work of human beings and communication devices that have already cameras installed used for communication and calls (to make videos and photos and videoconferences) and digital devices with access to entertainment and information channels and programs that human beings use frequently and for a long time for entertainment. Then, this is possible to mention that the dark and the elite offer technology to humans but deprive them of their privacy: Humans can use the technology of the darks and see everything dark offers but also dark see humans!! (which corroborates the eye in the triangle of the matrix of the so-called illuminati). However, this is accepted by most human beings the surveillance cameras installed in workplaces and even in schools, colleges and universities. But, this is objectionable that surveillance cameras are used in living places of coexistence because with this the family harmony and the privacy and intimacy of family members are lost. Thus, what is mentioned in the biblical scriptures about the nudity of the human being is fulfilled and about the loss of the family unión and the love in apocalyptic times (Mt. 24:12) (Dn. 12:4). Therefore and actually, the control and manipulation to induce to the concupiscence have reached the levels mentioned in the biblical scriptures about the persecution of Nazarenes (Mt. 24, Mt. 10:16) and even worse by using surveillance programs through the increase of the science and technology which is also used for the persecution to Nazarenes and induce to the concupiscence (Dn. 12,4).

- through strict restrictions and reduction of freedoms, confinement with subsequent compulsory vaccination to be able to access human rights such as the right to work and the right to travel example (with the cover-up of the

respective organizations responsible for it: OIT OMT), without the responsibility of the authorities in charge of vaccination worldwide (OMS) for the short or long term counterproductive effects of the vaccinated population due to the risk with the liquid of the vaccines by interfering with the DNA and RNA of the population.

- through the possible marking and elimination of many human beings (possibility also of control of the pulmonary alveoli or induction controlled of diseases or pain due a virus or introduction of liquid and solid chips in humans) in times of epidemic in medical examinations and treatments in hospitals (false medical negligence with breach of the medical oath of the use of Medicine for human good) with the possible introduction of liquid and solid chips in humans (liquid crystals that crystallize in the organism and installed in neurons and receive ultrasonic waves of very low frequency) (possibly inserted from vaccines in global epidemiological programs for population control or invasive medical examination when this is not necessary as a figurative example of review of a patient with a sore in the mouth and introduction of the whole hand in the throat or prostate examination or specific injections to certain objective humans or Nazarenes who have opened the matrix of the dark and the elite that controls humans in the Earth).

- through the possible human marking with liquid and solid chips introduced into the human being used for the control of humans: possible mind reading (telepath), thought induction (double direction: sending and receiving messages in the style of Stephen Hawking and in the style of the technology already used in send probes into space and to the moon). Therefore, humans who have the mind reader chip installed can speak without speaking (the dumb speak playing like the miracles of Jesus Christ). In addition, it is possible to detect if the humans who have the mental reading chip installed have psychological alterations without going to a doctor. Also, it is possible to know if humans are good or bad without seeing their actions and without going to a priest. In this way, human beings with the chip installed can be sanctioned before they do somewhat wrong (simply because it is known to be thinking). In addition, this can be used to know the fidelity to a political guideline or direction (this is known by the strong rumor in communist countries that already have the technology to detect the fidelity to the political party and possibly this is through this chip installed in the human being and mind reading). If in addition to mind reading, the inserted chip can perform thought induction, then this is possibly the apocalyptic mark mentioned in the apocalypse because many humans will perform sins or concupiscence induced and not natural. Then, this will most probably activate the Wrath of God, the seals and the trumpets of the apocalypse. Besides, it surprises that the OMS mentioned that want to insert manufacturing center of vaccines in many countries and inclusive surveillance programs if new viruses appear, but the word virus here is very probable to have been used in code to mention humans who are not in the control triangle of the matrix. Therefore, the manufacturing center of vaccines and surveillance programs is possible for the control and reduction of the population will be effective at the local level. Then, it is possible also the surveillance program to the human marking and possible creation of zombie humans for population control for the dark and elite in the new world order and in times of Tribulation

- Connection of covert surveillance cameras (in living and working places) with the mind reading chip and with channels of traditional technological devices through movies, programs and even newscasts (including newscasts that usually make signs of dumb and deaf to those who have already discovered them) used to manipulate, induce

concupiscence to the Nazarenes by the dark with the respective programs and channels. Therefore, humans who watch a program, movie, or news can be mentally tracked by their reactions and reflexes (surveillance cameras) or by their thoughts (mind reading chip) and in addition, to monitor and tracing to verify the induction to concupiscence through mind reading and surveillance cameras on line in the best style of James Bond espionage movies (including control of faces, pupils, irises, reflections, details, and diseases). In this way, this is a strong sign of apocalyptic and tribulation times and preparation of the technological apparatus for the control of the dark and the elite (and possibly the antichrist according to biblical scholars) in the program of the new world order and Tribulation.

- Games of judgments of sin against humans and Nazarenes (playing at being gods) and also profiting from the vile metal through the system and contributing to the persecution of the Nazarenes in times of Tribulation and new world order. In addition and with everything previously mentioned about mind reading and thought induction to induce concupiscence and sin, then, there are also fake judgments of sin against humans and Nazarenes because many of these sins have been induced with technology (and possibly by means of the chip) and have not been natural (dark inducing sin through technology and playing gods to induce evil). In this way, this (the game of humans playing gods: destruction of intimacy and privacy even in the mind of the human being and fake judgments of sin due to the thought induction) constitutes a strong sign of the last times and the prompt manifestation of the seals and trumpets of the apocalypse, manifestation of the Lamb of God and the sealed of the Apocalypse.

Retaliation to those who report surveillance and manipulation programs and marking of humans for mind reading and thought induction (making them sick sending to the hospitals or removing them).

- An accelerated program of new world order in Europe with digital identification plan and digital money to do digital control and avoid conflict and protests of marked and Nazarenes in surveillance programs who discover that there is no privacy in their documents and in their mind (telepathy: mind reading and thought induction) due to the total control of the dark in times of new world order and Tribulation. It surprises that EU mentions that have a digital plan for Europeans for digital control online. But, before the epidemy, Europe and all the world has advanced a lot in technology and the data of humans are digitally in hospitals and institutes that humans need. After, the EU mentions about artificial intelligence (possibly and most probable inside of human beings by means of chips) for the human being. Then and in vaccination and epidemy time, it is possible that digital control is a new digital control with artificial intelligence and with possible chips installed in the human being (possibly already installed in many human beings).

- Games of events and coincidences to cause accidents or conflicts in the life of marked, target or Nazarenes (change games of the victim to accused by companies that regulate the order with subsequent rectification of the game made by the same companies when the Nazarenes claim).

- Games of recognition of the identity of human beings by companies and service stations which are necessary for the daily movement of human beings, create conflicts of manipulation and stress in the marked or Nazarenes (in

the style of the movie Unknown, forgetting that the Eternal God Allah calls himself I am who I am!! when Jehovah answered Moses in the rescue of the Israelites from the Egyptians...but also mentions:... for myself, for the love of myself, I will do it so that my name will not be sullied, and my honor will not be given to another ... Myself, I am the first, I am also the last...!! (Is. 48))

- Salary payment games (payment of wages with dinners and game of check payment) create manipulation conflicts and stress in the life of marked, target or Nazarenes.

- Programmed plans of theft and scams of companies and enterprises even knowing of the surveillance cameras for the control of the marked, target or Nazarenes.

Then, there is a severe control of human beings in their daily activities to verify the follow-up of the matrix and dark that plan situation of concupiscence in the human being.

Besides, this is occurring in coincidence with an accelerated new world order program and possible tribulation times and possibly with the installation of the apocalyptic mark (possible chips introduced in the human being for mind reading and thought induction to induce concupiscence) in humans mentioned in the apocalypse for dark control of humans.

In addition, it is important to make evident, detail and specify the possible origin of the virus probably used for the control and manipulation of the population by viruses produced in Laboratories:

Viruses produced in the Laboratory creating epidemics and chaos on the Earth for the control and reduction of the population in times of the beginning of the new world order and possibly Tribulation according to biblical erudite

The reason for origin of the virus was initially attributed to animals such as bats or pangolins in human contact with them or by consuming them. The initial rumors were that the virus originated in a city in China. However, the Chinese have consumed bats and exotic animals for centuries and besides, it is part of the Chinese Culture and humanity has never presented an epidemic for this reason for centuries.

Thus, the theory of the origin of the virus through an animal is hardly credible. This is tremendously criticizable, the hypocrisy with which the information and communication media still try to make the population believe that the virus originated from an animal.

Then, this should not be surprising because the information and communication media (newscasts of traditional technological devices) obey the interests and convenience of the dark and the elite that control humans on Earth.

This is the same logic that applies to proponents of the theory of evolution who argue that man came from ape when apes did not evolve into humans from Adam to the present day. This example does not rule out that some species of birds and plants evolve and change in certain details, but not abrupt changes such as from ape to man.

The main reason for this is that we must accept that the Superior Entity Allah created all animal and human species and the entire cosmos at the beginning summarized in the Genesis [1] of the Bible Torah or Koran.

In the same way and with the same logic, it is very unlikely that the virus originated by consuming animals such as bats or pangolins when the Chinese have consumed these animals for centuries, which is recorded in their culture and without any consequence of epidemics.

Furthermore, humanity has previously had plagues and epidemics such as the black plague and Spanish flu without such strict measures of control, confinement and restriction of human freedoms. In this way, it is surprising that on the eve of a scheduled plan for humanity (new world order and program 2030), strict confinement measures and restrictions were carried out.

In addition, it was also rumored that the virus was brought from the US to China at a military Olympics event in China with the objective possibly to cover up the origin of the virus. Subsequently, there were accusations between the two countries, China and the US, where China accused the US of producing AIDS in a laboratory to spread it around the world. From these accusations between these powerful countries and by simple logic, it is evident that the virus originated in a laboratory (regardless of which country it originated in).

Because there are actually many virus laboratories in the power countries: China, US, Russia and some European countries, and these countries experiment with viruses very similar to SARS, it is very probable that the virus originated in a laboratory.

Therefore, we come to the conclusion that the origin of the virus of SARs is most probable from a laboratory (possibly for the control and reduction of the population through the introduction of liquid and solid chips in humans: liquid crystals that crystallize in the organism and installed in neurons and receive ultrasonic waves of very low frequency for lecture (telepathy) and induction mental).

In addition, humanity has previously had plagues and epidemics such as the black plague and Spanish flu without such strict measures of control, confinement and restriction of human freedoms.

Besides, SARs vaccine research laboratories have experimented since before the appearance of the virus, which suggests that this has been programmed with anteriority for humans.

In this way, it is surprising that on the eve of a scheduled plan for humanity (new world order and program 2030), strict confinement measures and restrictions were carried out.

It surprises me that actually the OMS wants to bring the vaccination program to Africa, when in Africa there are not many dead by the epidemy (possibly for the control and reduction of the population will be in all the Earth).

Afterward, the OMS mentioned that wants to insert a manufacturing center of vaccines in many countries and inclusive vigilance programs (possibly for the control and reduction of the population will be effective at the local level). But, what the OMS needs to mention is that it is necessary to eliminate the laboratories of virus creation and not create more vaccine laboratories. Humans do not want more vaccines and injections and laboratories for the creation of vaccines but the elimination of virus laboratories which are most probably used for the control and reduction of the population. However, the spreading of a virus created in a laboratory across the Earth by means of an epidemy with posterior vaccination has been a programmed plan of the dark and the elite for the control and reduction of the population in preparation for a global elite program (new world order or program 2030).

Therefore, this is understandable that many evangelists and biblical erudite mention that humanity is on a final straight towards the apocalypse and the fulfillment of the biblical prophecies of Tribulation, the opening of seals and trumpets, and the Wrath of God. In addition, there is the risk that a new virus will pass from the laboratory to a country or group in armed conflict on the Earth, and in this way, the virus will spread among humans to cause human destabilization and chaos in all the Earth.

Therefore, humanity must request the responsible organizations (OMS ONU), in addition to the elimination of nuclear and atomic weapons [7], and also the elimination of these virus laboratories.

Therefore, human beings must not believe everything said by organizations (ONU OMS) and individuals who control the Earth and who obey directions imposed within the matrix triangle of control of the Earth.

Therefore, it is very probable that the virus originated in a laboratory on the eve of an accelerated Program (new world order) by the dark desperate for control of the Earth which is happening in coincidence with the catastrophic climatic situation in the Earth and possible climatic signs of the Wrath of God [1] and with the claim by many biblical erudite that the Tribulation is about to begin in the Earth (Mt. 24: 7).

Besides, this is occurring in possible Tribulation times for bible believers who assure that in times of Tribulation biblical [1] prophecies must occur epidemic (Mt. 24) and possible marking of humans (Ap.13:16) for the control of the dark.

Then, this is necessary and essential for the Intervention of the Superior Entity (God Allah: Fort he love of myself and my chosen ones) in times of Tribulation [1] at the time timely due to everything mentioned in this document regarding the increase of inequity, discord and evil among humans.

This Intervention of the Superior Entity Allah is mentioned in the biblical scriptures [1] with the opening of seals (Apoc. 6) and trumpets (Apoc. 8:6) and with the full manifestation of the Lamb of God (Apoc. 5) and the sealed (Apoc. 7) chosen for the illumination and awakening of the Eternal's chosen people guided and taken to the New City of God: The New Jerusalem: New Heavens and New Earth (Apoc. 21)!!!.

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